

Genetic diversity of rice varieties in Tamil Nadu

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The genetic diversity of rice varieties released in Asia was investigated in 1979 by Hargrove, Coffman, and Cabanilla, IRRI. These authors expressed the view that the cytoplasmic similarity of modern rice varieties, although posing no immediate practical problem, is sufficiently relevant to demand a prompt broadening of the maternal genetic base of modern rices. They recommended the avoidance of the use of maternal derivatives of Cina as females in crosses, the naming of varieties of diverse maternal origin, and the identification and use of alternative sources of dwarfism.

The genetic diversity of rice varieties available in Tamil Nadu was investigated. The state has released 107 varieties; 68 are pure-line selections from traditional cultivars and 39 were developed by hybridization. Twenty-one other high-yielding varieties have been introduced into the state from outside since 1965 (Table 1). Thus 60 varieties developed by hybridization are available. Of that number 17 (28%) released before 1965 are tall varieties with local cultivars as their ultimate female progenitors.

In the varieties available after 1965 (71.7%), 21 have Cina, 8 have DGWG,

Table 1. Details on varieties either released or introduced in Tamil Nadu, India, through 1980.

	Varieties (no.)			Total
	Pure lines	Hybridization		
		Until 1965	After 1965	
<i>Varieties developed in Tamil Nadu</i>				
Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai	23	5	8	36
Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram	11	2	2	15
Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur	6	1	2	9
Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore	24	8	10	42
Multi Crop Experiment Sub-station, Palur	2	—	—	2
Deep-Water Rice Research Station, Talainayar	2	—	—	2
Saline & Alkaline Experiment Station, Peravurani	—	1	—	1
<i>Varieties introduced in Tamil Nadu</i>				
Total	68	17	43	128

Table 2. Ultimate female progenitors of varieties developed through hybridization in Tamil Nadu, India.

Ultimate female progenitor	Until 1965	After 1965	Total
Molagalagulu	1	—	1
ADT 2 (White Serumani)	1	—	1
ADT 3 (Kuruvai)	2	1	3
Norin 6	—	1	1
Norin 8	1	—	1
TKM 7 (Kullakar)	—	1	1
SR 26B (Kalamonk)	1	—	1
CO 3 (Vellaisamba)	1	—	1
CO 4 (Anaikomban)	2	—	2
CO 13 (Arupatham kodai)	1	—	1
PTB 15 (Kavunginpoothala)	—	2	2
Karneji	—	2	2
Manipur 36 (Japan Phon)	—	1	1
T 90 (Machakanta)	—	1	1
Basmati 370	—	2	2
GEB 24 (Kichili Samba)	7	2	9
DGWG (Dee-geo-woo-gen)	—	8	8
Cina	—	21	21
Not known	—	1	1
Total	17	43	60

and the other 14 have local cultivars as ultimate female progenitors (Table 2). All except IR5, NLR 9672, Ponni, White Ponni, and Bhavani carry the same semidwarfing gene from the semidwarf Chinese variety Dee-geo-woo-gen.

After their introduction TN1, IR8, and their derivatives were increasingly used in Tamil Nadu's crossing program. About 50% of the 43 varieties either released or introduced in Tamil Nadu after 1965 have the same maternal parent Cina, and thus have similar cytoplasmic components. The IRRI researchers suggested the use of new sources of semidwarfism such as Ponni Dwarf mutant, D66 (a mutant from Calrose), P3 Dwarf (a spontaneous mutant from Basmati Dehradun), and of alternate sources of maternal parents, which are readily available in the 68 pure lines already released by the State. ■

Isolation of composite rice cultures

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Because of genotypic differences, cultivars with similar morphology and flowering duration vary in their adaptation and yield potential. When mixed, such types may be suitable for different agroclimatic conditions. A trial to isolate composites with better adaptability was conducted at Ambasamudram during the 1980 kar (Jun-Sep).

The 11 trial varieties were raised in individual nurseries and in 55 combinations. For the combinations, seeds of two varieties were mixed at 1:1. The 66 treatments were transplanted at a 20 × 10-cm spacing at 2 seedlings/hill in randomized blocks with 3 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-50kg of N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha.

TM3447, TM2048, TM1927, and TM1898 showed variation in flowering and grain characters, and so were not good combiners. Among the combinations, nine showed uniformity for flowering, pigmentation, and grain characters.

Individual varieties and combinations differed significantly in grain yield but the component varieties vs combinations did not. AS693 yielded highest (7.1 t/ha), followed by AS691 (6.9 t/ha), AS764/2 (6.8 t/ha), and TKM9 (6.8 t/ha). The best varieties, however, were not always the best combiners. The combination AS687 + AS688 yielded highest (7.8 t/ha) and was comparable to 17 other combinations (range, 7.5-6.8 t/ha). Among them, six combinations involving AS687, AS688, AS691, and AS693 showed uniformity in flowering duration and grain characters as well as high yield potential (see table).